

Dissertation Research Proposal

01-16

Analysis of socio-natural hazards generated through rapid unplanned urbanisation in Himalayan towns: A case of Almora, India

Dresden Leibniz Graduate School

October 2016

Abstract

The Himalayan region is experiencing population growth and undergoing the process of rapid unplanned urbanisation. The urban development process is increasingly ignoring considerations of location, slope, drainage and vegetation to accommodate more people in limited land. This unplanned urbanisation coupled with growing number of extreme weather events is leading to the generation of socio-natural hazard risks like landslides arising from the interaction of anthropogenically modified slopes with high intensity rainfall. Taking the case of Almora, a Himalayan town in Uttarakhand, India, this dissertation analyses socio-natural hazards generated through the process of rapid unplanned urbanisation. Urban planning documents, field observations and interviews with residents, municipality officials, real estate developers and local NGOs form the basis of study. These are analysed, qualitatively and quantitatively, to establish the characteristics, extent, impact and drivers of socio-natural hazards. The results will contribute towards understanding the urban development challenges in often neglected yet rapidly urbanising Himalayan settlements. It will add to knowledge on socio-natural hazards and provide recommendations for addressing them.

1 Introduction

The Himalayas are the youngest and the loftiest mountain range in the world. They form a 2400 km long arch and cover an area of 6,00,000 square kilometres (Zurick et al. 2005). The area is characterized by difficult terrain, extreme weather conditions and the presence of several natural hazards like earthquakes and landslides. Harsh living conditions made it one of the last places to be colonized by humans in prehistory (Bellwood 2014). Until few decades ago the area was recognized as primarily rural with sparsely populated and scattered settlements.

This has dramatically changed in recent years. Politically divided between the countries of India (6 mountainous states), Nepal and Bhutan, the Himalayas have experienced a steady population growth (Table 1). There has also been a shift of population from rural areas to urban centres where economic avenues and access to services is better.

Table 1: Population and the share of urban areas in the Himalayas (Source: Compiled from Census of India 2011, Central Bureau of Statistics Nepal 2011, National Statistics Bureau Bhutan, 2005)

Country	Area (in Sq.Km)	Population (in Million)			Urban Population share (in %)		
		1991	2001	2011	1991	2001	2011
India (6 states)	425463	22.6	27.9	33.3	23	26	31
Nepal	147181	18.5	23.1	26.4	9	14	17
Bhutan	38394	0.5	0.6	0.7	16	25	37

However, the process of urbanization in the Himalayas has been haphazard and unplanned (Tiwari & Joshi 2012). Population pressure and economic incentives have pushed settlements to hazardous locations and practices of slope alteration, drainage pattern disruption and loss of vegetation have become more the norm than the exception (Rautela 2005). Municipalities, engaged in providing basic services, have weak or non-existent regulatory mechanism and poor integration with disaster risk reduction. The problem is further aggravated as, in addition to the natural hazards known to the region, incidents of climate change induced hazards like high intensity rainfall and glacial lake outburst floods are also increasing (Singh & Sharma 2014; Kohler et al. 2014).

This unplanned development scenario poses a twin risk to the future of fast growing urban areas in the Himalayas. The first is by increasing vulnerability in the face of a natural disaster. This became evident in the loss of life and destruction of property during the 2015 Nepal earthquake (Goda et al. 2015), 2014 Srinagar floods (Meraj et al. 2015) and the 2013 Uttarakhand cloudburst

(Satendra et al. 2015). Devastation caused in each case was increased due to multiple aspects of unplanned urbanization. The second is the generation of **socio-natural hazards**. This refers to hazards arising from anthropogenic practices that cause environmental degradation like slope modification or drainage disruption in the mountain. These on interaction with natural phenomenon like rainfall may result in landslide or flooding. These incidents are local and small scale and often do not warrant national emergencies or attention from international press (Pelling 2003). However, because of their continuous and cumulative nature, they account for environmental and economic losses and hamper the process of sustainable development.

This dissertation proposes to analyse the socio-natural hazards generated through the process of rapid unplanned urbanisation in the context of the Himalayas. This is done by identifying the characteristics, extent, impacts and drivers of this phenomenon.

2 Theoretical background: social production of risk

Goal 11 of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), adopted by the United Nations in September 2015, explicitly aims to ‘make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable’ (UN 2015). Target 11b further links this work to the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030 and aims at ‘adopting and implementing integrated policies and plans towards inclusion, resource efficiency, mitigation and adaptation to climate change, resilience to disasters’ (UN 2015). This is echoed in Habitat III’s Transformative Commitments for Sustainable Urban Development which pledges towards ‘resilience to disasters and climate change and other shocks and stresses’ (Habitat III 2016). This narrative shifts the focus of several disaster studies from hazard management to disaster risk reduction and its integration into settlement development to increase urban resilience. Much of the current global attention in this regard has been focused on coastal megacities which are at risk from rising sea levels (Revi 2014; Bicknell et al. 2009). Mountain habitats have remained peripheral to this discussion despite presenting several challenges owing to a multi hazard environment, high variability of terrain, remoteness and recent experiences with increased population and extreme weather events (Zimmermann & Keiler 2015).

With a steady rise in the number of inhabitants in an area predisposed to natural hazards, unplanned urbanisation in the Himalayas presents a tough developmental challenge (Rautela 2005; Tiwari & Joshi 2012; Singh & Sharma 2014; Nüsser et al. 2015). Hewitt & Mehta (2012) call for debunking of developmental stereotypes of the Himalayas being scantily populated scattered settlements. There is a need to recognise them as areas of rapid urbanization where human sources of danger are coevolving with natural hazards known to the region. This challenges the dominant approach adopted by hazard studies in recognising nature as primary cause of disaster.

Instead, it acknowledges the interlinkages between natural and human causes of hazard and the social production of risk (Hewitt 1983; Wisner 2004).

In the spectrum of hazards classified between natural and man-made, 'quasi-natural' hazards represent those hazards where natural and human forces act together (Smith 2004). UNISDR (2009) has further refined the concept and defined it as **socio-natural hazard** i.e 'the phenomenon of increased occurrence of certain geophysical and hydro meteorological hazard events, such as landslides, flooding, land subsidence and drought, that arise from the interaction of natural hazards with overexploited or degraded land and environmental resources'. The process of urbanisation that entails environment degradation often presents cases of socio-natural hazard production (Pelling 2003). Unlike natural hazards, socio-natural hazards can be managed or completely avoided through sustainable management of land and resources. This underlies their importance in disaster risk reduction. However socio-natural hazards study has received limited scientific as well as policy attention (UNISDR 2009). As they are chronic and small scale, they are often not registered in disaster records making it difficult to study them and to gauge their cumulative impact (Bull-Kamanga et al. 2003).

Though several studies have been undertaken to assess the vulnerability of the structures in the Himalayas to earthquakes (Rautela 2010; Anhorn et al. 2015), assessment of socio-natural hazards remains a grey area. Some authors point towards disregard of mountain terrain, location safety, natural drainage and vegetation to be associated with socio-natural hazard production (Sah & Pande 1987; Anbalagan 1993; Rautela 2005; Sati et al. 2011). In the advent of a rainfall event this often leads to landslides and collapse of structures. However, others contest that because of the close linkage to a natural trigger, it remains difficult to objectively associate human intervention with disaster risk (Ives & Messerli 1989; Haigh & Rawat 2012).

Previous studies on addressing socio-natural hazards generated through unplanned urbanisation in the Himalayas place the onus of responsibility on the municipalities and suggest stricter and mountain specific developmental regulations (Kumar & Pushplata 2013). Reintroduction of traditional practices known for resilience towards hazards which are disappearing with high pressure on land is also suggested (Rautela 2015). However, as most towns are small in size and remote in location, they often do not have the institutional or financial capacity to address the issue (Rumbach 2016). Thus much of the urbanisation is happening at a fast pace and in spite of governance. In this scenario, the role of private stakeholders like real estate developers and non-governmental organisations needs to be acknowledged and investigated. Furthermore, policy alternatives besides institutional reforms need to be explored (Pelling 2003; Masson 2015). This must be done keeping in view community aspirations as investigation into the rationales for living in hazardous zones indicate that perspective economic gains are beginning to outweigh hazard awareness among residents (Lennartz 2013).

3 Research questions and hypotheses

This dissertation aims to analyse the emerging concept of socio-natural hazards generated through the process of unplanned urbanisation in the Himalayas. The focus is on high altitude (>600m) ridge towns where flat land is limited and urbanisation takes place on steep slopes. The overall research question is:

How can Himalayan towns address socio-natural hazards generated through rapid unplanned urbanisation?

This is divided into sub-questions:

1. What **physical characteristics** of unplanned urbanisation are associated with socio-natural hazard generation in Himalayan towns?
2. What is the **extent** of unplanned urbanisation associated with socio-natural hazard generation in Himalayan towns?
3. What are the **impacts** of socio-natural hazards generated through unplanned urbanisation in Himalayan towns?
4. What **drives** unplanned urbanisation in Himalayan towns?
5. **What can be done** to address socio-natural hazards risk generated through unplanned urbanisation?

Based on the current state of literature and preliminary site investigations, the following hypotheses are proposed:

1. **Environmental degradation** to provide space for urban development is associated with socio-natural hazard risk generation in Himalayan towns.
2. **Majority** of the development in Himalayan towns is unplanned and does not take socio-natural hazard risk generation into account.
3. Large scale unplanned urbanisation is **increasing the risk** of socio-natural hazards.
4. **Absence of regulatory mechanism, development driven by private real estate developers and lack of potential risk awareness among residents** is driving unplanned urbanisation in the Himalayas.
5. **Integration of urban planning with disaster risk reduction measures and its effective implementation, incentivising safe development and engagement of local environmental organisations to increase risk awareness** can check unplanned urbanisation and address socio-natural hazard risk generation.

4 Research design and methods

The research adopts a **case study design** to answer the research questions. The rapidly urbanising ridge town of Almora, in the Himalayan state of Uttarakhand, India is taken as a case study. Location on a high ridge (1642 meters), absence of a strong regulatory framework and increasing pressure on urban land are the primary criteria for selection. Its population grew from 26,001 in 1991 to 34,122 in 2011 and is currently divided into 11 administrative wards (Census of India 2011). It has an administrative area of 7.35 sq.km and experienced an 80.73 % increase in built up area between 1990 and 2010 (Rawat 2015) . It is thus representative of a rapidly urbanising unplanned Himalayan town.

Figure 1: Map of Himalayas indicating the position of Almora town (source: Artificial Reason)

Figure 2: Map of Almora town indicating built area (source: J.S Rawat)

The research is carried out in three broad stages:

Phase-I: Establish an **analytical framework** to assess socio-natural hazard potential.

Scope: Socio-natural hazards can be caused by a variety of factors. This dissertation limits itself to the investigation of physical factors established in literature vis-à-vis location, slope, drainage and vegetation.

Phase-II: Data collection in Almora town on **extent, impact and drivers** of socio-natural hazard generated through unplanned urbanisation and analysis of data.

Scope: Absence of a land use map and information on risk zonation presents a challenge for research. Hence the creation of a base map and establishing terrain characteristics will be part of the research. However, geotechnical investigations are beyond the scope of work.

Phase III : Recommendations to address socio-natural hazards in Almora.

A description of research design and methods adopted is provided below:

How can Almora address socio-natural hazards generated through rapid unplanned urbanisation?			
Research Question	Data	Method	Expected Outcome
Phase – I (establishing analytical framework)			
1. What physical characteristics of unplanned urbanisation are associated with socio-natural hazard generation in Almora?	<p>Literature on socio-natural hazards in Himalayas (Sah & Pande 1987; Rautela 2005; Haigh & Rawat 2012; Anbalagan 1993)</p> <p>Development guidelines and Building bylaws: a) National: URDPFI guidelines b) State : Uttarakhand Building bylaws c) Local : Municipal bylaws Almora</p> <p>Globally prescribed good practices for mountain areas (UNISDR, GFDRR)</p>	<p>Based on the three sources of data a set of characteristics in relation to location, slope, drainage and vegetation will be identified.</p> <p>These characteristics will further be categorised based on physically discernible features with potential for risk generation into low, medium and high categories.</p>	Framework for assessment of physical characteristics of unplanned urbanisation with potential for socio-natural hazard risk generation
Phase – II (data collection and analysis)			
2. What is the extent of unplanned urbanisation associated with socio-natural hazard generation in Almora?	<p>Primary data on the nature of location, slope, drainage and vegetation of urban development as per the assessment framework.</p> <p>Photographs recording representative cases.</p>	<p>Field observations based on assessment framework will be carried out in 1 wards (core, periphery or suburb) of Almora comprising of approximately 750-800 houses.</p> <p>House level mapping of data collected on a GIS platform with a contour base map.</p> <p>Spatial Analyst Tools to generate maps indicating low, medium and high risk for each attribute under study.</p>	Risk maps showing number of households with potential for socio-natural hazard risk generation
3. What are the impacts of socio-natural hazards generated through unplanned urbanisation in Almora?	<p>Primary data from residents in study area on past disaster events</p> <p>Records in the Disaster mitigation cell, Almora</p> <p>Local newspaper records from last 10 years</p>	<p>Questionnaires distributed in households in the study area</p> <p>Review of literature</p>	Tabulation of past disaster events associated with unplanned urbanisation

Research Question	Data	Method	Expected Outcome
<p>4. What drives unplanned urbanisation in Himalayan towns?</p>	<p>Primary data from:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Residents in study area 2. Government Agencies : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> State level : <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Uttarakhand Housing and Urban Development Authority b) Disaster Mitigation and Management Center, Uttarakhand Local level: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Almora municipality b) Disaster Mitigation Cell, Almora 3. Private/Non-Governmental Agencies: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Real estate developers b) Local Environmental NGOs (Uttarakhand Seva Nidhi, Green Hills Almora) 	<p>Questionnaires to residents on rational for development choices and awareness of potential risk generation.</p> <p>Semi-structured interviews with:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Government representatives at state and local levels on institutional challenges in controlling unplanned urbanisation. b) Real estate developers on land availability, prices and focus on safety measures in the development process. c) Local environmental NGO on their capacity and developmental vision. 	<p>Quantitative assessment of : Residents' development choices and awareness on hazard risk generation</p> <p>Qualitative assessment of : a) Challenges faced by government departments c) Role and knowledge of real estate developers b) Capacity and vision of local environmental NGOs</p>
<p>Phase – III (Recommendations)</p>			
<p>5. How can socio-natural hazards risk generated through unplanned urbanisation be addressed?</p> <p>Based on the outcome of research questions 1-4, recommendations for future development for the municipality, NGOs, real estate developers and citizens will be formulated.</p>			

5 Work programme

The work program follows the research method. Each stage is accompanied by continuous literature review and written drafts. The year is divided into quarters (Q1-Q4).

References

- Anbalagan, R., 1993. Environmental hazards of unplanned urbanization of mountainous terrains: a case study of a Himalayan town. *Quarterly Journal of Engineering Geology*, 26(3).
- Anhorn, J., Nusser, M. & Lennartz, T., 2015. Rapid urban growth and earthquake risk in Musikot, Mid-western hills, Nepal. *Erdkunde*, 69(4).
- Bellwood, P.S. ed., 2014. *The global prehistory of human migration*, Wiley-Blackwell.
- Bicknell, J., Dodman, D. & Satterthwaite, D., 2009. *Adapting cities to climate change : understanding and addressing the development challenges*, London ;Sterling, VA : Earthscan.
- Bull-Kamanga, L. et al., 2003. From everyday hazards to disasters: the accumulation of risk in urban areas. *Environment and Urbanization*, 15(1), pp.193–204. Available at: <http://eau.sagepub.com/cgi/doi/10.1177/095624780301500109> [Accessed July 29, 2016].
- Census of India, 2011. Primary Census Abstract Data Tables. Available at: <http://censusindia.gov.in/pca/pcadata/Houselisting-housing-UK.html>.
- Goda, K. et al., 2015. The 2015 Gorkha Nepal Earthquake: Insights from Earthquake Damage Survey. *Frontiers in Built Environment*, 1, p.8. Available at: <http://journal.frontiersin.org/Article/10.3389/fbuil.2015.00008/abstract> [Accessed July 28, 2016].
- Habitat III, 2016. Habitat III Zero Draft for the New Urban Agenda.
- Haigh, M. & Rawat, J.S., 2012. *Landslide causes: Human impacts on a Himalayan landslide swarm Les impacts humains sur une séquence de glissements de terrain dans l'Himalaya*, National Committee of Geography of Belgium / Société Royale Belge de Géographie.
- Hewitt, K., 1983. *Interpretations of calamity from the viewpoint of human ecology*, Boston: Allen & Unwin.
- Hewitt, K. & Mehta, M., 2012. Rethinking risk and disasters in mountain areas. <http://rga.revues.org>, (100-1).
- Ives, J.D. & Messerli, B., 1989. *The Himalayan dilemma : reconciling development and conservation*, London ;New York: United Nations University.
- Kohler, T., Wehrli, A. & Jurek, M. eds., 2014. *Mountains and climate change: A global concern*, Sustainable Mountain Development Series. Bern, Switzerland, Centre for Development and Environment (CDE), Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation (SDC) and Geographica Bernensia. Available at: http://www.cde.unibe.ch/about_us/news_archive/e298084/e311190/LOW_Fullversion_Mountain_ClimateChange_english_eng.pdf [Accessed August 29, 2016].
- Kumar, A. & Pushplata, 2013. *Building regulations for environmental protection in Indian hill towns*,
- Lennartz, T., 2013. Constructing Roads—Constructing Risks? Settlement Decisions in View of Landslide Risk and Economic Opportunities in Western Nepal. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1659/MRD-JOURNAL-D-13-00048.1>.
- Masson, V. Le, 2015. Considering Vulnerability in Disaster Risk Reduction Plans: From Policy to Practice in Ladakh, India. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1659/MRD-JOURNAL-D-14-00086.1>.
- Meraj, G. et al., 2015. Assessing the influence of watershed characteristics on the flood vulnerability of Jhelum basin in Kashmir Himalaya. *Natural Hazards*, 77(1), pp.153–175. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11069-015-1605-1>.
- Nüsser, M., Dame, J. & Schmidt, S., 2015. Urbane Entwicklung im indischen Himalaya. Die Beispiele Srinagar und Leh. *Geographische Rundschau*.
- Pelling, M., 2003. *The vulnerability of cities : natural disasters and social resilience*, London ;Sterling VA: Earthscan Publications.
- Rautela, P., 2005. Increasing vulnerability of the Himalayan urban centers. *Disaster prevention and management*.
- Rautela, P., 2010. Seismic vulnerability and risk in the Himalayan township of Mussoorie, Uttarakhand, India. *Current Science*, 99(4).
- Rautela, P., 2015. Traditional practices of the people of Uttarakhand Himalaya in India and relevance of these in disaster risk reduction in present times. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 13.

- Rawat, J., 2015. Monitoring land use cover change using remote sensing and GIS techniques: A case study of Hawalbagh block, district Almora, Uttarakhand, India. *Egyptian Journal of Remote Sensing and Space Science*, 18(1).
- Revi, A., 2014. Towards transformative adaptation in cities: the IPCC's Fifth Assessment. *Environment & Urbanization*, 26(1).
- Rumbach, A., 2016. Disaster Governance in Small Urban Places: Issues, Trends, and Concerns. In *Disaster Governance in Urbanising Asia*. Singapore: Springer Science+Business Media.
- Sah, N.K. & Pande, R.K., 1987. Construction Activity and Environmental Degradation in Almora Town in the Central Himalaya. *Mountain Research and Development*, 7(1), p.71. Available at: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3673325?origin=crossref> [Accessed August 1, 2016].
- Satendra et al., 2015. *Uttarakhand Disaster 2013*, New Delhi .
- Sati, S.P. et al., 2011. Recent landslides in Uttarakhand: nature's fury or human folly. *CURRENT SCIENCE*, 100(11).
- Singh, S.P. & Sharma, S., 2014. Urbanisation Challenges in the Himalayan Region in the context of Climate Change Adaptation and Disaster Risk Mitigation. In Bangalore, India: International Congress on Green Urban Futures.
- Smith, K., 2004. *Environmental hazards : assessing risk and reducing disaster*, London ;New York : Routledge.
- Tiwari, P.. & Joshi, B., 2012. MRI_News7_Tiwari-Joshi.pdf. *Mountain Research Initiative Newsletter*. Available at: mri.scnatweb.ch/en/docman-main/1865-mri...no...urban-growth-in-himalaya/file.
- UN, 2015. Sustainable Development Goals. Available at: <http://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/sustainable-development-goals/> [Accessed July 27, 2016].
- UNISDR, 2009. 2009 UNISDR Terminology on Disaster Risk Reduction. *International Strategy for Disaster Reduction (ISDR)*, pp.1–30. Available at: www.unisdr.org/publications.
- Wisner, B., 2004. *At risk : natural hazards, people's vulnerability, and disasters*, London ;New York : Routledge.
- Zimmermann, M. & Keiler, M., 2015. International Frameworks for Disaster Risk Reduction: Useful Guidance for Sustainable Mountain Development? *Mountain Research and Development*, 35(2), pp.195–202. Available at: <http://www.bioone.org/doi/full/10.1659/>.
- Zurick, D. et al., 2005. *Atlas of the Himalaya*, Kathmandu: ICIMOD.